

Review Article

Tolvaptan - Vasopressin Antagonist for Hyponatremia

Kondeti Venkata Surya Siva Kumar¹, Saripella Latha Sree² and Saripella Jaya Sree³

Department of Pharmacology and Pharmaceutics, Chebrolu Hanumaiah Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Chandramoulipuram, Chowdavaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh – 522019, India

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23 July 2023

Accepted: 25 July 2023

Published: 01 Aug 2023

Keywords:

ADPKD; polycystic kidney disease; position statement; tolvaptan; vasopressin V2 receptor antagonist

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.8206257

ABSTRACT

The groundbreaking TEMPO 3:4 trial, which served as the basis for tolvaptan's approval, represented a revolution in the treatment of autosomal dominant polycystic kidney disease (ADPKD). Through this advancement, patient management for ADPKD has evolved from using broad strategies to stop the progression of chronic kidney disease to focusing on disease-specific mechanisms. Evidence-based strategies to start treatment only in patients with quickly worsening disease are essential, though, given the long-term nature of this medication and associated side effects. The European Renal Association (ERA) policy statement, released in 2016, was the first society-based guideline on the usage of tolvaptan and has been a popular resource for nephrologists when making decisions. Since then, there has been a significant accumulation of practical knowledge regarding the use of tolvaptan in ADPKD.

INTRODUCTION

The most frequent electrolyte imbalance among hospitalized patients is hyponatremia. Hyponatremia, which affects 5.5% of patients [1], is characterized by a drop in serum sodium levels and symptoms ranging from nausea to convulsions and coma. Both the rate of salt loss and the level of absolute sodium concentration affect the occurrence and severity of these symptoms. In addition to the syndrome of inappropriate antidiuretic hormone (SIADH), excessive hydration during exercise, nephritic syndrome,

cirrhosis, heart failure (HF), and the use of specific medications, hyponatremia is not the main diagnosis [2].

Although there are many different potential causes of hyponatremia, arginine vasopressin (AVP) is almost always involved. The anterior hypothalamus generally releases AVP in response to a rise in plasma osmolality, a fall in blood volume, or a rise in blood pressure (BP). Following its production, AVP activates many subtypes of AVP receptors all over the body.

*Corresponding Author: Kondeti Venkata Surya Siva Kumar

Address: Department of Pharmacology and Pharmaceutics, Chebrolu Hanumaiah Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Chandramoulipuram, Chowdavaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh – 522019, India

Email ✉: venkatasurya317@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Contrary to hyponatremia associated with HF, which is caused by an increased AVP secretion secondary to a decreased effective arterial blood volume that is unrelated to sodium concentration, hyponatremia associated with SIADH results from the incomplete suppression of AVP due to a variety of causes [2].

Structure of Tolvaptan

Mechanism of Action:

Compared to natural AVP, tolvaptan is a vasopressin antagonist with higher affinity and selectivity for the V₂ receptor. Reduced aquaporin-2 channels in the renal collecting tubules as a result of antagonistic activity at the V₂ receptor lead to decreased water reabsorption, an overall increase in free water excretion (aquaresis), and an increase in serum sodium levels. The increase in serum sodium concentration is purely due to aquaresis; this decrease in free water is not accompanied by an increase in sodium or potassium ion excretion [2].

Pharmacokinetics

Absorption and Distribution

Tolvaptan's total bioavailability is unclear, although oral administration results in at least 40% of the medication being absorbed. Peak effects are four to eight hours after administration, and two to four hours after the start of an effect. The bioavailability of tolvaptan, as well as the beginning or duration of its effects, do not appear to be impacted by taking it with food.

Tolvaptan is 99% bound to circulating plasma proteins after absorption. Patients with moderate-to-severe hepatic impairment and HF have a higher volume of distribution (around 3 L/kg), but this does not impact the patient's reaction to the

medication. Tolvaptan distribution is not known to be impacted by renal impairment [3].

Indications

For patients with hypervolemic and euvolemic hyponatremia, including those with HF, cirrhosis, and SIADH, tolvaptan was licensed for use in the U.S. in May 2009. Hyponatremia is characterized in this situation as a serum sodium level of less than 125 mEq/L. If a patient has symptoms and they haven't improved with fluid restriction, their serum sodium level, which should be between 125 and 134 mEq/L, may need to be treated [2].

Medical Suitability / Clinical Efficacy

Two sets of phase 3 clinical trials were used to assess tolvaptan's effectiveness: the Efficacy of Vasopressin Antagonism in Heart Failure Outcome Study with Tolvaptan (the EVEREST Programme) and the Study of Ascending Levels of Tolvaptan in Hyponatremia [4,5,6].

The SALT Trials [7]:

To evaluate the outpatient use of tolvaptan for hyponatremia related to different causes, two randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind trials were carried out concurrently. Additionally evaluated were the medication's safety and reversibility of effect. Although SALT-1 and SALT-2 used the same methodology, they were conducted simultaneously to meet regulatory criteria. Patients who were 18 years of age or older and had hyponatremia (sodium levels < 135 mEq/L) due to HF, cirrhosis, or SIADH were eligible to participate in the trials.

Patients were excluded who:

- Had a reversible etiology of hyponatremia were disqualified from the SALT studies.
- Had a blood sodium level below 120 mEq/L together with neurological pathologies, such as psychogenic polydipsia, progressive or episodic neurological disease (including cerebrovascular accidents), or neurological disability.

- Had a cardiopulmonary component, such as severe angina, severe pulmonary hypertension, myocardial infarction (MI), ventricular tachycardia, or fibrillation.
- Had recently undergone surgery.
- Had a Child-Pugh Score of 10 or above, a serum creatinine (Cr) level over 5 mg/dL, or urinary obstruction.
- He had uncontrolled type 2 diabetes.
- It was unable to withstand abrupt changes in fluid pressure and volume.
- It had a slim chance of surviving in the short term.

Stratification of the enrolled patients was done based on the degree of hyponatremia. For the first 30 days, they either received tolvaptan or a comparable placebo. According to a protocol that called for gradual correction of serum sodium (no more than a 12-mEq/L increase in 24 hours and an absolute serum sodium concentration not higher than 145 mEq/L), the dose was started at 15 mg orally once daily and thereafter titrated to a maximum of 60 mg once daily. At the time of randomization, all patients were admitted to the hospital, and the majority of them were released by day four. Patients underwent a reassessment on day 37 after the conclusion of active treatment on day 30.

The main results were changes in the area under the curve (AUC) of the serum sodium concentration from randomization to days 4 and 30. The secondary endpoints were categorical serum sodium levels (i.e., normal, mild, or marked) for patients with obvious hyponatremia at randomization, change in the AUC concentration of sodium in patients with marked hyponatremia, absolute change in serum sodium levels, time until sodium concentrations normalized, percentage of patients with normal sodium levels at days 4 and 30, and time to sodium concentration normalization.

In the SALT-1 experiment, 102 patients received tolvaptan, whereas 103 received a placebo. In SALT-2, 123 patients received tolvaptan, while 120 received a placebo. Patients participating in each study group in both studies were comparable in terms of demographic and clinical traits, including the cause of hyponatremia, except height.

In SALT-1, 77.5% of those using the study medication and 63.1% of those taking a placebo finished the full 37-day experiment. In SALT-2, 74.8% of those using the study medication and 74.2% of those taking a placebo finished the full 37-day experiment.

The primary endpoint of the experiment, a rise in the AUC concentration of sodium at days 4 and 30, was significantly improved by tolvaptan (Table 2) (Table 2). Fewer tolvaptan patients than placebo patients showed marked hyponatremia at days 4 and 30, according to the analysis of the secondary endpoints. On day 1 (P 0.001 for all comparisons), patients who received tolvaptan had considerably increased urine output and significantly greater net fluid loss. There was no significant difference in the number of patients needing fluid restriction (P = 0.08 for each study), even though sodium and fluid status had improved.

Table 1: Changes in the Area under the Curve (AUC) of the Serum Concentration of Sodium in the SALT Trials

Variable	SALT-1		SALT-2	
	Tolvaptan	Placebo	Tolvaptan	Placebo
<i>Change (mEq/L) for all patients</i>				
Day 4	3.62 ± 2.68	0.25 ± 2.08	4.33 ± 2.87	0.42 ± 2.56
Day 30	6.22 ± 4.10	1.66 ± 3.59	6.20 ± 3.92	1.84 ± 3.83

SALT = Study of Ascending Levels of Tolvaptan in Hyponatremia

*All values are mean ± standard deviation

‡ $P < 0.001$ for all comparisons

There was no difference in the Physical Component Summary for health status indicators. The combined analysis of SALT-1 and SALT-2 ($P = 0.02$) and the combined scores of patients with substantial hyponatremia from both investigations ($P = 0.04$) also revealed a significant difference in the Mental Component Summary. Analysis of all patients recruited in SALT-1 revealed a difference ($P = 0.04$), however, SALT-2 patients showed no difference at all.

In conclusion, tolvaptan increased serum sodium levels in patients with a range of illness conditions effectively in the outpatient setting, and serum sodium levels returned to baseline once tolvaptan was stopped. The goal of the SALT research was not to demonstrate a survival advantage or long-term security.

The EVEREST Clinical Status Trials ¹⁸¹

A prospective, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study called the EVEREST Programme was carried out at 359 locations in North America, South America, and Europe. Three trials made up the program: two short-term studies examined how tolvaptan affected clinical status and outcomes, and the third research examined how all of the patients from the short-term trials fared over the long term.

Tolvaptan was given to usual therapy, which included diuretics, in Trials A and B to see if it would result in short-term clinical benefits in an inpatient setting. Tolvaptan or a placebo was initially given to subjects in a random order. According to a predetermined protocol, patients were then assigned to trial A or B depending on the total number of patients enrolled and the geographic location at the end of the study.

Similar to the SALT trials, the inclusion criteria required participants to have a documented left ventricular ejection fraction of 40% or less within the year before randomization and to have been

hospitalized with deteriorating New York Heart Association (NYHA) Class III or Class IV HF.

These criteria were used to exclude people:

- Patients who presented with acute MI, unstable hemodynamics, or anemia (hemoglobin below 9 g/dL) were excluded.
- Patients who had end-stage refractory HF, including recent cardiac surgery, cardiac mechanical support, or biventricular pacemaker placement, were ineligible to enroll based on their history.
- Hemodialysis patients, those with serum creatinine levels above 3.5 mg/dL, and those with potassium levels higher than 5.5 mEq/L were excluded from the investigations since tolvaptan is removed through the kidneys.

Within 48 hours of admission, enrolled patients were randomly assigned to receive tolvaptan 30 mg orally daily or a placebo in addition to standard HF treatment, which includes digoxin, hydralazine, ACE inhibitors, ARBs, beta-blockers, diuretics, and nitrates. Up to the conclusion of the lengthy study, the intervention was ongoing.

The primary outcome, a composite score of changes in self-assessed global clinical status and body weight from baseline to day 7 or at discharge, whichever came first, was analyzed in patients. The following secondary objectives were also measured: body weight at days 1 and 7 or discharge; global clinical status at day 7 or discharge; patient-assessed dyspnea at day 1 if dyspnea was present at baseline.

Throughout the trial, patients were monitored for adverse events constantly. Throughout the hospital stay, vital signs were checked daily, and blood chemical profiles were assessed on days 1, 7, and at discharge. Upon discharge and on days 1, 3, 6, and 8, electrocardiograms were analyzed.

4,133 patients were included in EVEREST; 2,048 patients received tolvaptan (1,018 received it; 1,030 received a placebo), and 2,085 patients

received tolvaptan (1,054 received it; 1,031 received a placebo) in study A. The demographic and clinical features of the two groups at the beginning of each study were comparable. 54 patients in trial A and 50 patients in trial B stopped taking their medications before day 7 or being let go from the hospital. Of these, 12 tolvaptan-treated patients and four placebo-treated individuals stopped their treatments.

Patients in trials A and B both demonstrated statistically significant improvements in composite global clinical status and body weight at day 7 or discharge concerning the primary outcome (P 0.001 for both studies). On day 1, more patients taking tolvaptan who had dyspnea at baseline had improvement (76.74% vs. 70.61%; P 0.001 for trial A; 72.06% vs. 65.32%; P 0.001 for trial B). Both tolvaptan and the placebo had comparable effects on the overall clinical status throughout the two studies (P = 0.51 for trial A and P = 0.52 for trial B).

At days 1 and 7 or discharge, tolvaptan was linked to greater body weight decreases in both trials (P 0.001 for all comparisons). Pedal edema at day 7 or discharge greatly changed. Patients receiving tolvaptan reported higher treatment-emergent side events, dry mouth, and thirst during the safety analysis. Throughout the course of the trial, there were no discernible variations in blood pressure, heart rate, renal failure, abnormal electrolytes, or abnormal liver function. During the inpatient stay, the tolvaptan arm dramatically decreased dyspnea, rales, orthopnea, jugular venous distention, and the dosage of furosemide, according to a post hoc analysis.

When tolvaptan was used in conjunction with standard medication, the EVEREST Clinical Status Trials showed a short-term reduction in body weight and dyspnea in hospitalized patients with HF, but no improvement in overall clinical status. Long-term data on clinical status or mortality were not measured in this investigation.

The EVEREST Outcome Trial ¹⁹¹

To assess the long-term impact of tolvaptan therapy on clinical outcomes, the EVEREST Outcome Trial enrolled all patients who had been randomly assigned to the initial series of trials. The same inclusion and exclusion requirements as for the short-term trials applied to patients. Patients participated in the study for a minimum of 60 days following randomization, which included both the initial in-patient hospitalization and the follow-up period. Follow-up continued until patient withdrawal, death, or the specified end of the research. A median time of 9.9 months was spent observing the patients.

All-cause mortality and a composite of cardiovascular death and hospitalization for HF were the main outcomes. Both superiority and non-inferiority analyses were conducted on all-cause mortality, while only a superiority analysis was done on the composite.

The composite of cardiovascular mortality or hospitalization was one of the secondary outcomes.

Cardiovascular death rates.

- How frequently HF becomes clinically worse.
- An adjustment in body weight on day one.
- The sodium level on day 7 or, if the baseline sodium level was < 134 mmol/L (134 meq/L), at discharge.
- If edema was present at baseline, edema at day 7 or discharge.
- If dyspnea was present at baseline, dyspnea was on day 1.
- The variation in the overall summary score on the Kansas City Cardiomyopathy Questionnaire (KCCQ) during the first outpatient week.
- The KCCQ domains changed at the beginning and conclusion of treatment, as well as during the first and fourth outpatient weeks.

The same randomization process used for the short-term trials was used to assign patients. 2,072

patients received tolvaptan and 2,061 received a placebo in this trial. 115 participants in the placebo group and 137 participants in the tolvaptan group withdrew from the study due to adverse events. Thirst was the sole adverse event that tolvaptan-related patients experienced more frequently than placebo-related patients in seven patients ($P = 0.02$).

Tolvaptan did not statistically outperform the placebo in the analysis of all-cause mortality. 537 patients (24.9%) who received tolvaptan died, compared to 543 (26.3%) who received a placebo (hazard ratio [HR], 0.98; 95% confidence interval [CI], 0.87-1.11; $P = 0.68$). However, tolvaptan did show in the non-inferiority analysis that it was not inferior to the standard of care ($P = 0.001$). The composite endpoint of cardiovascular death and hospitalization for HF did not improve with tolvaptan therapy (HR, 1.04; 95% CI, 0.95-1.14; $P = 0.55$).

Tolvaptan did not affect the composite of cardiovascular mortality or hospitalization, cardiovascular death, or the incidence of clinically worsening HF in a statistically significant way for the secondary endpoints. However, considerably more patients who got tolvaptan reported lessened dyspnea on day 1 than those who did not (74.3% vs. 68.0%, $P = 0.001$).

The treatment of tolvaptan also caused a substantial reduction in body weight on day 1 ($P = 0.001$) and a significant increase in pedal edema on day 7 ($P = 0.003$). Tolvaptan caused greater increases in serum sodium (mean [standard deviation], tolvaptan, 5.49 mEq/L [5.77 mEq/L], placebo, 1.85 mEq/L [5.10 mEq/L], $P = 0.001$) as well. Beginning on day 1 and continuing until week 40 of the trial, this impact was noticed.

The KCCQ overall summary score did not change at week 1, but at the end of the study, there were significant improvements in the quality-of-life domain ($P = 0.003$), the social limitation domain

($P = 0.05$), and the overall summary score ($P = 0.02$) at the final on-treatment assessment.

6.5% of patients taking tolvaptan and 5.5% of patients taking a placebo stopped taking the trial medicine as a consequence of adverse effects. Thirst was the only side effect that tolvaptan users experienced more frequently ($P = 0.02$). The incidence of renal failure or hypotension did not differ significantly across the groups, and both groups experienced similar long-term declines in blood pressure and heart rate.

In terms of mortality or rehospitalization, the EVEREST Outcome Trial did not show that tolvaptan was superior to normal care, but it did show that this medication was not subpar. In terms of dyspnea, pedal edema, and quality of life, tolvaptan also outperformed the placebo.

DOSAGE^[3]

Adults

To ensure proper therapeutic monitoring, patients starting tolvaptan therapy should be hospitalized. The first dosage is 15 mg taken orally once daily, regardless of mealtime. The dose should only be increased once every 24 hours, up to a daily maximum of 60 mg. For the first 24 hours of therapy, fluid restriction shouldn't be implemented to prevent a quick adjustment of the salt level.

Particular Populations^[3]

Age extremes. Tolvaptan is not licensed for use in pediatric patients, and no information is known regarding its use in young individuals. Aged people don't require dosage modifications.

systemic malfunction. Patients with hepatic or cardiac impairment don't require dosage adjustments. Patients with a creatinine clearance (CrCl) of 10 mL/minute or more do not require dosage modifications when using tolvaptan, which has been examined in patients with renal impairment. Patients with a $CrCl \leq 10$ mL/minute have not been investigated with the medication. Tolvaptan shouldn't be used in anuric patients

because of the drug's mechanism of action; no benefit is anticipated in these people.

Drugs And Drugs ^[3]

Tolvaptan has a wide range of medication interactions, however, compared to conivaptan, the size of these interactions is substantially reduced. Tolvaptan still shouldn't be used with powerful CYP 3A4 inhibitors including clarithromycin, ketoconazole, itraconazole, and many protease inhibitors, despite reduced interactions. It also might work less well when used with strong CYP 3A4 inducers like rifampin. Tolvaptan should be used with P-glycoprotein inhibitors like cyclosporine, so dose reductions should be taken into account. Tolvaptan may raise digoxin concentrations, but it does not affect warfarin (Coumadin, Bristol-Myers Squibb) or amiodarone (Cordarone, Wyeth) pharmacokinetics. Digoxin and lovastatin (Mevacor, Merck) did not affect the pharmacokinetic characteristics of tolvaptan.

Urinary volume when tolvaptan is administered concurrently with furosemide (Lasix, Sanofi-Aventis) or hydrochlorothiazide is comparable to that when tolvaptan is administered alone. When used with ACE inhibitors, type II ARBs, and potassium-saving diuretics, tolvaptan may result in an increased risk of hyperkalemia.

CONCLUSION

The first oral vasopressin antagonist is tolvaptan. Clinical trials have shown that it can reduce dyspnea and edema in HF patients without inducing renal failure, and it is effective at bringing serum sodium concentrations back to normal in a variety of conditions. These findings suggest that the medication is a suitable alternative for treating SIADH in patients. Tolvaptan should not be included in the usual pharmacological regimen for HF because it has not yet demonstrated a mortality benefit in individuals with the condition. A longer-term mortality advantage or a certain subset of HF patients who

may have lower mortality may be able to be identified in future studies.

REFERENCES

1. Zilberberg MD, Exuzides A, Spalding J, et al. Epidemiology, clinical and economic outcomes of admission hyponatremia among hospitalized patients. *Curr Med Res Opin.* 2008;24(6):1601–1608.
2. Verbalis JG, Goldsmith SR, Greenberg A, et al. Hyponatremia treatment guidelines 2007: Expert panel recommendations. *Am J Med.* 2007;120(11A):S1–S21.
3. Rockville, MD: Otsuka America Pharmaceutical, Inc.; May 2009. Samsca (tolvaptan), package insert.
4. Schrier RW, Gross P, Gheorghiade M, et al. for the SALT Investigators Tolvaptan, a selective oral vasopressin V2-receptor antagonist, for hyponatremia. *N Engl J Med.* 2006;355:2099–2112.
5. Gheorghiade M, Konstam MA, Burnett JC, et al. for the EVEREST Investigators Short-term clinical effects of tolvaptan, an oral vasopressin antagonist, in patients hospitalized for heart failure: The EVEREST Clinical Status Trials. *JAMA.* 2007;297:1332–1343.
6. Konstam MA, Gheorghiade M, Burnett JC, et al. for the EVEREST Investigators Effects of oral tolvaptan in patients hospitalized for worsening heart failure: The EVEREST Outcome Trial. *JAMA.* 2007;297:1319–1331.
7. Schrier RW, Gross P, Gheorghiade M, et al. for the SALT Investigators Tolvaptan, a selective oral vasopressin V2-receptor antagonist, for hyponatremia. *N Engl J Med.* 2006;355:2099–2112.
8. Gheorghiade M, Konstam MA, Burnett JC, et al. for the EVEREST Investigators Short-term clinical effects of tolvaptan, an oral vasopressin antagonist, in patients hospitalized for heart failure: The EVEREST Clinical Status Trials. *JAMA.* 2007;297:1332–1343

9. Konstam MA, Gheorghiade M, Burnett JC, et al. for the EVEREST Investigators Effects of oral tolvaptan in patients hospitalized for worsening heart failure: The EVEREST Outcome Trial. JAMA. 2007;297:1319–1331.
10. Structure of Tolvaptan - <https://web.chemdoodle.com/demos/iupac-naming#customise-template>
11. Indian Pharmacopoeia - 2022, Ninth Edition, Volume – III, Page number: 3832, Chebrolu Hanumaiah Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Chowdavaram, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India.

HOW TO CITE: Kondeti Venkata Surya Siva Kumar, Saripella Latha Sree and Saripella Jaya Sree, Tolvaptan - Vasopressin Antagonist for Hyponatremia, Int. J. in Pharm. Sci., 2023, Vol 1, Issue 8, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8206257>